

THE FAILURE PROCESS IN CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Conventional metallic materials have been tailored in the past close to their ultimate properties. New technological requirements ask for further improved materials. Metal matrix composites (MMC) promise to reach this goal, especially when reinforced with continuous fibres. Due to the increasing potential use of MMC's an overview will be given to the fracture behaviour of various MMC's. Especially studied will be aluminium and titanium alloys reinforced with carbon and various ceramic fibres. The main failure mechanisms and their development will be presented.

1. INTRODUCTION

In many technical areas extreme material properties are needed. High strength and stiffness should be combined with high temperature retention and low specific gravity. MMC can fulfill these needs. With fibre reinforcement improved stiffness and strength can be achieved when compared to metals. If additionally a higher temperature retention is needed, then fibre reinforced plastics reach their limit at about 200°C. However, fibre reinforced metals can further be used. Their application temperature is mainly dependent on the matrix material used [1,2].

The principal fibres which are currently available and of potential interest for use in MMC are listed in Table 1 [3].

The ceramic non-oxide SiC fibres have, because of their low reactivity to the metal matrix, a high potential for technical application. The oxide fibres, mainly the Al₂O₃ based fibres, are already used in technical parts, because they are relatively cheap, have suitable mechanical properties and their reactivity to the molten metal is low.

The high variability in the mechanical properties of carbon fibres, along with their high thermal stability, makes them to the ideal reinforcement for metals. However, the reactivity of carbon fibres with the metallic matrix very often reduces the superior fibre properties in the composite. Carbon fibres, therefore, generally need a protective coating, which increases fibre cost.

The main matrix materials which found attention are the light metals magnesium, aluminium and titanium. The idea of MMC is to strengthen the matrix by adding a second phase, the fibres or

Table 1. Mechanical properties of various types of fibres [3].

Fibre-type	Trade	Density [g/cm ³]	Diameter [mm]	Tensile Strength [MPa]	Elastic Modulus [GPa]	Strain to Failure [%]	α^* [10 ⁻⁶ k ⁻¹]
C-Fibre	T300	1,75	7	3430	230	1,5	-1,5
	HM 35	1,79	6,7	2350	358	0,6	-0,5
α -Al ₂ O ₃	FP	3,9	20	1500	380	0,4	6,4
SiC	Tyranno	2,4	10	2800	200	1,5	3,1
	SCS-6	3,05	140	3400	420	1	3,0

* α =coefficient of thermal extension

particulates. Strengthening of the matrix can easily be achieved if continuous long fibres are used. The mechanical properties follow the rule of mixtures. The possibility of matrix strengthening is indeed an advantage of metal matrix composites, however, it has the drawback that intensive internal stresses are built up, which have to be considered.

1.1 Fibre Matrix Compatibility

Fibre-matrix combinations are seldom in state of equilibrium; thus in most systems fibre and matrix will tend to interact usually with detrimental effects on the composite properties. The main interaction phenomena are [4]:

- fibre dissolution in the matrix
- fibre dissolution and reprecipitation (coarsening processes)
- chemical reaction between fibre and matrix
- segregation and/or precipitation of matrix constituents at the interface
- poisoning of fibres by matrix atoms
- thermal expansion mismatch

Apart from the last, the above phenomena are diffusion-dependent and, therefore, increase in importance with increasing temperature and time of exposure. Thus for most composite systems production methods are sought with as low temperatures and times as possible. Provided they survive manufacture, composites with potentially incompatible constituents can be used to certain temperature limits. To achieve a strong fibre reinforcement, the fibres must be reserved to prevent extensive chemical reactions between fibre and matrix. This can mainly be achieved by coating the fibre surface. The main techniques to be used are chemical vapour deposition (CVD) and physical vapour deposition (PVD).

To achieve a strong and tough fibre reinforced material the interface also has to seek detrimental requirements which are [5]:

- a weak interface, to achieve longitudinal strength and toughness by fibre debonding;
- a strong interface for good transverse properties.
- Further, ease of fabrication, including good wetting of the fibres if the matrix is combined in the liquid state, depends critically on interface chemistry for most economical processing methods.

The criteria to be satisfied will vary depending on the fibre, the matrix and application of the composite. There is, therefore, no given set of rules dictating chemical engineering of the interface

of optimized properties. Contradictory demands have to be fulfilled what shows that interface chemistry has to be further studied.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Results discussed in this paper are from experiments performed on a number of materials which contain various high strength fibres of different manufacturers. The fibres chosen for investigation were the HM35 carbon fibre from Toho Beslon, the SCS-6 fibre from Textron, the SiC fibre (Tyranno) from Ube, and the α -Al₂O₃ FP fibre from Dupont. The matrix materials were the aluminium matrix: for the C-fibre (HM35) and the Tyranno fibre pure as Al 1070 or with the FP-fibre as an Al-2,5Li alloy. The SCS-6 fibre was used to reinforce the Ti6Al4V titanium matrix.

Table 2. Properties of neat metal matrices

Neat Matrix	Elastic Modulus [GPa]	Tensile Strength [MPa]	Strain to Failure [%]
Al 1070	69	59	40
Al-2,5 Li	80	160	~25
Ti 6 Al 4 V	110	1100	8

The mechanical properties of the neat matrix alloys are given in Table 2. The pure aluminium matrix (Al 1070) has a comparatively low fracture stress, but a high strain to failure. When using the Al-2,5Li matrix, coherent $\bar{\Gamma}$ particles form leading to a precipitation hardening. Therefore, a relatively high fracture stress \bar{A}_B can be observed. Using lithium as an alloying element also increases the Young's modulus. The titanium matrix has the highest Young's modulus and fracture stress with the lowest strain to failure.

Manufacturing of the Al-composites occurred by various squeeze casting techniques; only in the case of the C-Al system the composites were produced by hot pressing aluminium coated carbon fibres, following the prepreg route [6]. During consolidation at temperatures above 580°C, fibre matrix interactions can occur. The most prominent is the formation of reaction products, as Al₄C₃ carbides in the C-Al system. Masson et al. [7] show that the carbides have a needle-like structure and grow both into the fibre and into the matrix. They harm the fibre by forming cavities and, therefore, reduce their strength. The SCS-6/Ti6Al4V was manufactured by a diffusion bonding process via hot isostatic pressing (HIP).

Tensile and compressive tests were performed on the unidirectional composite with fibres in the 0° and 90° direction. In addition, fatigue tests were made at a stress ratio of R=0.1 and R=-1, respectively.

3. MATERIAL CHARACTERISATION

Static Loading: In Table 3 the mechanical properties after tensile and compressive testing for both 0° and 90° fibre orientation are summarized [3,8]. The strain to failure is controlled by the fibre failure strain. However, under compressive loading the strength is considerably higher than in tension, which is in agreement with a higher strain to failure under compressive loading. The generally good compressive behaviour can mainly be related to the fact that:

- The metal matrix itself has a relatively high Young's and shear modulus, which allows to better support the fibres and avoids their short wave kinking.
- The ceramic fibres themselves, because of their micro-structure, can carry a higher compressive than tensile load.

- The higher fibre diameter increases the moment of inertia, thus delaying fibre microbuckling.
- In the unidirectional composite residual tensile stresses are stored in the matrix and residual compressive stresses in the fibres. Due to this, the matrix in a composite is in the unloaded condition in a status marked by (*) in Fig. 1. Under tensile loading only a small portion of the metal elastic strength remains and it early starts to deform plastically. Under compressive load, however, only elastic and no plastic deformation is observed, because the composite matrix has now for its deformation the whole compressive elastic and the additional residual stress part (tensile part) available for deformation. Full support of the fibres with only elastic matrix deformation remains therefore available over a wider range of loading [9].

Table 3. Mechanical properties of SiC-Al, Al₂O₃-AlLi and SiC-Ti6Al4V after tensile and compressive testing

a)	[0°] SiC-Al		[90°] SiC-Al	
	Tension	Compression	Tension	Compression
σ_B [MPa]	920	1605	168	204
ϵ_B [%]	0,89	1,77	1,30	7,80
E [GPa]	125	118	102	90

b)	[0°] Al ₂ O ₃ /Al-2,5Li		[90°] Al ₂ O ₃ /Al-2,5Li	
	Tension	Compression	Tension	Compression
σ_B [MPa]	538	1460	177	225
ϵ_B [%]	0,36	1,09	1,20	7,40
E [GPa]	181	166	126	117

c)	[0°] SCS-6/Ti 6 Al 4 V
	σ_B [MPa]
ϵ_B [%]	1,1 - 1,3
E [GPa]	190 - 230

In a test transverse to the fibre direction, the fracture stress of the composite exceeds the fracture stress of the matrix. Due to the fibre reinforcement also an increase of the Young's modulus can be observed.

Besides the fact that the matrix material has a high strain to failure, it cannot be realized in the composite. Only about 1.2% strain to failure can be achieved. Under compressive loading the Young's modulus is not as high as in tension; but the fracture stress is again essentially higher. Therefore, the strain to failure is by far higher under a compression loading than under tensile loading.

Fig. 1 Schematic of the matrix stress/strain behaviour in tension and compression, to illustrate internal stress state.

The strength of a metal matrix composite strongly depends on the fibre-matrix interaction. In Table 4 the fracture stress of a carbon fibre reinforced aluminium is given [6]. Due to the processing temperature the fibre matrix interface is influenced. For longitudinal specimens a low processing temperature (580°C, 15 min) leads to only few fibre-matrix interactions with a weak interface and pronounced fibre pull-out [3], but a relatively high fracture stress. At a high processing temperature (600°C, 30 min) with extensive fibre-matrix interactions [5] the strong interface results in fast crack propagation with a relatively plane interface and a reduced fracture stress. The longitudinal strength depends on the temperature and the time during C-Al processing. Transverse to the loading direction just the opposite can be observed. At high processing temperatures, due to good fibre-matrix bonding because of fibre-matrix interactions, higher fracture stresses can be

Table 4. Tensile properties of C-Al dependent on processing temperature

C/Al		[0°]		[90°]	
		600 °C 30 min	580 °C 15 min	600 °C 30 min	580 °C 15 min
σ_B	in MPa	445	638	33	8
ϵ_B	in %	0,38	0,45	0,11	0,03
E	in GPa	154	175	34	30

realized, as in the case of poor bonding (at low processing temperatures). A sufficiently good C-Al composite can probably only then be produced, when a protective fibre coating is developed, which suppresses fibre-matrix interactions.

4. DAMAGE MECHANISMS

In a composite material, loaded in the fibre direction, not only the fibre and matrix strength or the fibre volume fraction play an important role, but the fibre/matrix interface properties are also critical. The presence of either good or weak bonding influences the composite properties [6] and the damage mechanisms occurring. Due to the interface strength various damage mechanisms can be observed, which are schematically shown in Fig. 2. These include debonding at the crack tip,

debonding in the crack wake, frictional sliding between the fibre and matrix, fibre failure and fibre pullout with additional frictional sliding. The most important role to the composite failure plays the interface strength. If a fibre fails in a composite, the matrix transfers the load from the broken fibre into the neighbouring ones. The transfer length is partly dependent on the interface strength.

In the case of a good bonding the transfer length is smaller than in the case of a weak bonding. This has an essential influence on the fracture morphology. In Fig. 2 the fracture morphology due to the interface strength is schematically given. In the case of a weak bonding (Fig. 2a) the fracture morphology is dominated by fibre pullout. The fracture surface is extremely irregular. If one fibre fails, no stress transfer occurs through the matrix, as an immediate debonding happens [6].

In the case of intermediate bonding fracture occurs with only few fibre pullout; the crack jumps from one fibre to the neighbouring one with extensive matrix deformation. The matrix forms dimples around each broken fibre (Fig. 2b). A stress transfer is possible, however, at the fibre fracture, when the maximum shear stress builds up, some debonding occurs due to additional matrix deformation. The matrix tends to yield. Extensive tensile stresses perpendicular to the fibre direction occur [3].

Fig.2 Crack path morphology as a result of fibre matrix bonding (schematically).
a) weak bonding
b) intermediate bonding
c) good bonding

In the case of a very good bonding multiple fracture of the fibres is observed (Fig.2c), due to the fact that around a crack a stress field exists. Through the matrix the load (stress) is directly retransferred into the fibre, and it will fail again. Important is, that in this case, failure occurs via a propagating crack, which forms a plastic zone around and ahead of the crack tip, leading to a stress increase at the very crack tip. Because of this "too good" bonding the maximum fracture stress cannot any more be achieved [10].

In fibre reinforced composites the damage behaviour under compressive loading is significantly different from the behaviour under tensile loading. The major damage mode under compressive loading is a short wave kinking of the 0°-fibres. Due to this short wave kinking is the formation of a shear band with the result, that the fibres fail, loaded both in compression and shear (Fig. 3). The preferred locations for short wave kinking are:

- Matrix rich areas. Less support to the fibres can be given, as in the case of a homogenous fibre distribution.
- Pores, which due to their size, significantly ease fibre kinking.
- Insufficient fibre alignment and fibre distribution.

- Plastic deformation of the matrix, which especially at elevated temperatures, limits the compressive strength.

Fig. 3 Schematic of short wave kinking

In the case of composite failure when loaded transverse to the fibre direction, quite different damage mechanisms can be observed. When loaded in tension the stress concentration at the fibre/matrix boundary initiates early failure. However, the fibre matrix bond strength has an essential influence on composite failure and various damage mechanisms can occur, as summarized in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Failure mechanisms in a $[90^\circ]$ -composite under tensile loading, schematically.

- a) weak bonding
- b) intermediate bonding
- c) good bonding
 - c1) matrix failure
 - c2) fibre splitting

In the case of poor bonding between fibre and matrix interfacial fracture is favoured in a transverse tensile test (Fig. 4a), and the stress concentration caused by tension perpendicular to the fibre also contributes to the interfacial fracture. The crack follows the fibre/matrix interface and in some cases, circumferential cracks are formed around 90° -fibres as a result of tensile loading [10].

In the case of an intermediate bonding a mix of various types of failure can be observed (Fig. 4b). A fibre/matrix debonding, the formation of dimples on the fibres, giving rise to the assumption of locally high plastic deformations, and fibre shear failure can be observed together and occur simultaneously [10].

In the case of good bonding two main types of damage can be distinguished (Fig. 4c). Failure occurs in the matrix either by matrix shear or in a tensile manner of the matrix, associated with the formation of dimples, which means, that locally extensive plastic deformations occur. An extremely strong fibre matrix bonding can also yield longitudinal splitting of the fibres.

Macroscopically compressive failure in an isotropic alloy occurs because of shear stresses on the planes 45° to the loading axis. This is in general also true for unidirectional composites, however, shear failure occurs in the planes which exhibit the fibre direction. Micromechanically compressive failure occurs, because tensile stresses are induced at the fibre matrix boundary transverse to the loading direction. Failure initiates in tension at the fibre matrix boundary leading to a highly irregular crack front along the fibre/matrix boundaries. But also matrix shear failure can be observed at certain locations. The superior compressive stresses, when compared to the tensile stresses are related to the fact that:

- Under a compressive load the crack tends to shear in the 45° direction. The fibres support each other, respectively the irregular crack front hooks up.
- Failure initiates under compressive load in transverse tension at the fibre/matrix interface.

5. SUMMARY

Properties of unidirectionally fibre reinforced metal matrix alloys were investigated. Designers and engineers seem not to be aware that metal matrix composites have their greatest potential when loaded in compression. No other engineering material is known to the author having similar properties.

References

1. Chou, T.W., Kelly, A., Okura, A., *Composites* 16(1985) p.187.
2. Stöckel, D., *Faserverbundwerkstoffe*, in: *Metallische Verbundwerkstoffe*, 1977, p. 132.
3. Schulte, K., Minoshima, K., *Proc. 12th Riso Nat. Symp. on Materials Science: Metal Matrix Composites*, Hansen et al., Eds., Riso Nat. Lab., Roskilde, DK, 1991, p. 123.
4. Warren, R., *Proc. 9th Riso Int. Symp. on Metallurgy and Materials Science*, Andersen et al., Eds., Riso Nat. Lab., Roskilde, DK, 1988, p. 233.
5. Mortensen, A., in [4], p. 141.
6. Masson, J.J., Weber, K., Miketta, M., Schulte, K., in [3], p.509.
7. Masson, J.J., Kleine, A., *Proc. IPCM '91*, J. Verpoest, Ed., Butterworth-Heinemann, Oxford, 1991, p. 232.
8. Schulte, K., Trautmann, K.-H., Girot, F., *Z. Materialprüfung*, 32(1990) p.343.
9. Schulte, K., Trautmann, K.-H., Leucht, R., Minoshima, K., *Proc. ASTM Symposium on Cyclic Deformation, Fracture and NDE of Advanced Materials*, Miami, FL, USA, Nov. 1992, to be published as ASTM-STP.
10. Schulte, K., Minoshima, K., *Composites* 24 (1993) p.197.